

Significance of Anticipatory Stage in the Formation of Psychological Contract for Effective Recruitments by Contemporary Organizations

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Abstract

In the recent days it has been highly discussed about unemployment problems across India by many political and non-political bodies. According to economic times, the unemployment rate if compared with previous rates, is 45 year high. But, in reality we also have come across many examples of reasonably skilled candidates rejecting the offers they have received, mainly due to 'lack of feel' to enter into an employment contract.

This lack of feel leads us to the concept of 'Psychological Contract' (PC), which is an unwritten and undocumented mental agreement existing between employee and employer. But in India it is least explored as a cause for voluntary unemployment. PC has three stages namely, anticipatory stage or pre-employment stage, early socialization stage and latter stage. The contract initiates with the anticipatory stage which is focussed in this paper.

Though the concept of PC has quite a long history, many of them have been focussing more on breach of PC while only some researches have focussed on its formation and development.

This paper attempts to establish the causal relationship of existence of a psychological contract during the pre-employment stage for effective recruitments.

Keywords: Psychological contract (PC), formation of PC, anticipatory or pre-employment stage, recruitments.

Introduction

Meaning and Background

In recent days psychological contract (PC) has been one of the attention catching areas for the researchers in the field of human resources management. Although the term hints that it is related to psychology, its implications are more with HRM. A psychological contract (Argyris 1960; Rousseau 1989) is a perceived mutual

obligation existing between an employee and an employer (Schein, 1978; Conway & Briner, 2005; Kelly Windle & Kathryn von Treuer, 2014) the changes in which may affect the relationship existing between the employee and his/her employer, either positively or negatively.

Stages in Psychological Contract

While the business environment is day by day becoming highly dynamic, expectations from the job seekers and employees are becoming increasingly complex to achieve. This gap between the expectations and that exist in the reality gives rise to different stages in the PC.

There are many studies that have thrown light on the entire process of psychological contract, beginning from formation until the breach of the contract, prominently indicating three major stages, which are – Anticipatory stage, early socialization stage and the latter stage (Kelly Windle & Kathryn von Treuer, 2014). The importance of stages in PC are as shown in Fig 1.

The anticipatory or pre-employment stage begins with some basic level expectations formed in the job seeker's mind regarding the first job (Rousseau, 2001) such as company environment, compensation, colleagues, work location, friendly supervisor, nature of the job etc.

Early socialization is the next stage which is formed when the job seeker enters the organization. That is when he/she tries to match or compare their expectation with their reality, which can either exceed their expectation or can fall behind the same. In former case the rough foundation for the contract built transforms into a stronger one and in the latter, it might loosen.

During the latter stage, the employee exhibits certain behaviour that indicates the level or strength of the contract which depends on the outcomes of early socialization stage.

However the researches done to support these stages are very limited due to lack of empirical evidence (Harrison, Ashforth & Sluss, 2007).

Hence this paper tries to establish relation between attitude and aptitude status at the pre-employment/anticipatory stage and find out of that has a strong correlation towards their future employment status.

Figure 1 Types and Stages of PC

(Source: Kelly Windle & Kathryn von Treuer 2014)

Role of Anticipatory Stage in Formation of PC

Though it is after a formal education a candidate enters into an organizational set up, the initiation and development of the Psychological Contract begins at the time of education (anticipatory stage). It is the education system that moulds a person's attitude, mind set and behaviour according to the requirement of the business environment. If contract development of a person is constructive during this stage, he is most likely to exhibit a positive PC and high productivity during early

socialization and latter stages. Conversely, if contract development is poor, it might result in low productivity, absenteeism, frequent job hopping etc. as the candidate might not succeed in adapting to the dynamic business environment.

The strength of contract is different from person to person. For instance, a person whose post-graduation (PG) level score is more than under-graduation (UG) level, indicates improvement in the psychological contract which might have positive impact on getting employed. But there are several complexities for a successful psychological contract formation during the anticipatory stage. This paper focusses on identifying and studying these complexities and its underlying causes.

Objectives of the Study

1. To establish and analyse the complexities during anticipatory stage of Psychological contract.
2. To develop the causal loop with possible influencing factors for the psychological contract.

Literature Review and Research Gap

Several researchers have attempted to study the concept of PC since quite a long time. The concept of psychological contract was initially explained by Argyris (1960) and later developed by Schien (1965) and Rousseau (1989). Their study also implies that the concept of PC was very closely related to Blau's social exchange theory (1964).

Jacqueline A-M et al (2008) from London school of economics and political science specifies in SAGE handbook of organization behaviour that the basic foundation to formation of psychological contract begins from the society in large. Schools, family, peer groups, social interactions have a greater role in formation of PC. The author attempts to explain the concept of PC by reviewing hundreds of literatures. They specify that number of assumptions are made by a person before and during their first employment regarding their job, salary, work environment, recognitions etc. These assumptions give rise to a psychological promise made by the employee. In other words, this is the anticipatory stage of PC.

Denise M Rousseau et al, (2013), elucidates in their study about conceptual framework of psychological contract. They explain not just formation and importance of PC and its formation, but also about breach of the contract and its impact on contemporary organizations. According to them, reaction to psychological contract breach is theorized to be stronger than unfulfilled expectations, although expectations during pre-employment might positively impact on formation of PC.

P. Matthijs Bal and Tim Vantilborgh (2018), in their article titled "Life span perspectives on psychological contract" discusses various phases of PC, including development, growth and maturity. They also specify how the contract might change by considering age as one of the major factor. They argue that, it is very important for the company to understand how relationships and expectations changes over time with young, middle-aged and older workers, in order to keep their employees motivated and satisfied. Based on socio-emotional selectivity theory, it can be predicted that younger workers have greater interest in development compared to older workers. And this highlights the importance of anticipatory stage of PC for effective recruitments.

Kelly Windle and Kathryn von Treuer (2014) attempts to develop a model that establishes a relationship between types of psychological contracts and stages in it (the model is as shown in Fig. 1. They explain different types of PC and how it influences during different stages.

Research Gap

There are many researchers studying the concept of PC all around the world. However it was found that that empirical evidence to justify the formation and development were less due to a fact that many studies have been mainly focussing on other areas of PC such as industrial case studies,

breach of contract etc. but very few have considered formation and development, which gives the scope for future studies on the same.

Also, many researches highlight that developing positive job related mind set in today's young generation is becoming increasingly difficult as they tend to have a lot of expectations from their job. Besides education, a suitable intervention must also be designed and applied to address this issue.

Research Methodology

The paper tries to explain the importance of anticipatory stage for effective recruitment by analysing the data obtained from 49 samples (selected using convenience sampling) who had undergone one week of training exclusively on employable skills.

Primary data is obtained by consolidating the scores of pilot test conducted after the training, along with their academic scores of UG and PG (since all the candidates are still pursuing their final year MBA, aggregate of first year was used to assess the results).

Secondary data was collected through journals, magazines, linked in articles, news-papers etc.

There are many studies which have tried to establish the importance of training during anticipatory stage and the impact of this stage in overall formation of PC. This study endorses those researches along with specifying the necessity for suitable interventions to address this issue. Hence the study is confirmatory in nature.

Since the paper deals with understanding of underlying causes for weak or strong formation of PC during anticipatory stage and its effects on the recruitments, the research design used here is Causal.

Both descriptive and inferential statistical tools were used to analyse and interpret the data. To find out relationship existing between the variables, correlation test was used, while to understand if the potential of the contract is changed or remains the same from one stage of education (UG) to another (PG), a hypothesis was developed and analysed using T test even if the sample size is 49, since the samples used are not true random samples.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

This paper is a result of the analysis from a pilot test conducted to a group consisting of 49 post graduate students. The intention was to find out the causes responsible for development of the PC during anticipatory stage and how it impacts on recruitments. This was measured by willingness of the student to attend the interviews during campus placements.

A descriptive statistics were computed for the variables under consideration in order to understand the nature the distribution of the sample. The calculated values are tabulated as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Descriptive Analysis

	UG Aggregate Score	1 year PG Aggregate Score	Average Aptitude Score	Attitude Score	Willingness Score
Mean	0.698226531	0.670536735	0.684381633	0.474635569	0.314868805
Median	0.7	0.67	0.68	0.457142857	0.285714286
Mode	0.7	0.68	0.655	0.285714286	0.142857143
Standard Deviation	0.087669195	0.033407439	0.057234537	0.234507468	0.206154439
Kurtosis	-0.765517518	-1.13751051	-0.943630131	-0.792224453	-0.715700847

Skewness	-0.116959606	0.113010101	0.031752965	0.330959508	0.364147632
Range	0.34	0.12	0.215	0.942857143	0.714285714
Minimum	0.52	0.61	0.58	0.028571429	0
Maximum	0.86	0.73	0.795	0.971428571	0.714285714

To test if there is some influence of academics on the formation of the contract, corresponding details such as aggregate result of their UG and PG courses (referred as aptitude) were collected from the students. These details were analysed along with the scores obtained by students during employability skills training offered to them for one full week and number of interviews attended by the students out of seven companies offered (referred as attitude and willingness). These companies belonged to various sectors including Marketing/Sales, HR, Finance and stock broking.

The following observations were made from the analysis:

- There was a visible reduction in overall results from UG to PG. This may be because of factors such as over confidence, lack of flexibility and willingness to learn which indicate reduced contract, or may also be because of any other genuine issue such as health, managing work and studies, family issues etc.
- Out of 49 students the maximum result in UG was 86% and minimum result was 52%, In PG the maximum and minimum results decreased to 73% and 61% respectively. While the most repeated result in UG was 70%, in PG it was 68%.
- Negative kurtosis indicates that the distribution is more flat, not following the standard normal curve. In other words it has more peaks without clear central tendency.
- Negative skewness is seen in case of UG, due to the fact that the mean is lesser than median. Other cases, positive skewness is seen since mean is larger than median.
- The average willingness score is 31%, which indicates the deteriorated interest level of students to attend the interviews even during the campus recruitments.

This study focussed to identify the influence of variables under consideration in Table 1, on the potential strength of an intended PC. Hence Pearson's correlation coefficients were computed and tabulated as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Pearson's Correlation Coefficients

	UG Aggregate	I year Aggregate	Mock Interview Score	Willingness (Acceptance/Rejection)
UG Aggregate	1			
I year Aggregate	0.734297232	1		
Mock Interview Score	-0.041668411	-0.012574601	1	
Willingness (Acceptance/Rejection)	0.080332946	0.233413131	0.151050776	1

The following observations were made from Table 2:

- There is a strong positive correlation between UG and PG scores (0.734).
- There is mild positive correlation between training and willingness to attend the interview.
- There is no visible correlation between the remaining variables.

As it is observed from the Table 1, the mean difference in the academic scoring from UG program

to PG program appeared to be marginal. But the correlation coefficient in Table 2 is strong. Hence, the t-Test was adopted to check the difference in mean of the two samples.

Null hypothesis (H0)

There is no significant in the two means of academic scores

Alternative hypothesis (H1)

There is significant difference between means of two academic scores.

Table 3 t-Test Paired Two Sample for Means

	I year PG Aggregate marks	UG Aggregate marks
Mean	0.670536735	0.698226531
Variance	0.001116057	0.007685888
Observations	49	49
Df	48	
t Stat	-2.889194452	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.002890314	
t Critical one-tail	1.677224196	

From the Table 3, the following observations were made

- As the reduction in mean values were observed in Table 1, a one tail t-Test was adopted.
- Since the t Stat is greater than t Critical, the difference in two means are significant.

Conclusion and Future Scope

The value of mean scores decreased from UG level to PG level, indicating decrease in the potential for a favourable psychological contract in offered recruitment drives.

The study aimed at finding out the complexities during anticipatory stage in formation of psychological contract. Reduced interest, lack of flexibility and learnability, unwillingness to attend the interviews were found to be the major convolutions in formation of the PC. This indicates the possibility of reduced academic performance acting as an “inhibitor” for favourable psychological contract between students and employer(s).

Though there is a positive correlation between aptitude (academic scores) and attitude (willingness to attend the interview), it is not strong enough to determine causal relationship. Hence these issue requires development of suitable interventions and different metrics to capture the causal loop.

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